

On the sparseness and structure of the normal equations for the abscissa solution (Step 1)

L. Lindgren 79-10-17 (ESTEC)

1. Number of stars per set

Let a set consist of m_0 ~~scans~~ consecutive scans, overlapping (at the antinodes) by 50% of the width (Φ) of each scan. The covered region has the following form (Fig. 1):

Fig. 1

The total solid angle covered by the set is approx.

$$A = 2\pi\Phi + 2(m_0-1)\Phi \quad (1)$$

If $n_s = 10^5$ is the total number of stars, the number of stars in the set is $n_{set} = \frac{n_s}{4\pi} \cdot A$, see Table below.

m_0	n_{set} ($n_s = 10^5, \Phi = 0.9^\circ$)
1	785
2	1035
3	1285
4	1535
5	1785
6	2035
	⋮

} = 785 + 250(m-1)

The stars in the set are numbered $i = 1, 2, \dots, n_{set}$ according to increasing abscissa: $w_1 \leq w_2 \leq \dots \leq w_{n_{set}}$.

2. Sparseness of normal equations

The unknowns involved in Step 1 are of two kinds:

- the "global" unknowns: basic angle, scale, grid distortion terms, attitude angles (parameters common to the whole set);
- the "local" unknowns: the star abscissas.

There may be $l \approx 25-50$ (?) global unknowns in a set, while the number of local unknowns are of course $n_{set} \approx 1785$ ($m_s = 5$). If the global unknowns are placed first in the list of unknowns, the normal eq. matrix has the following structure (Fig. 2):

The matrix elements in the shaded areas (in total $l^2 + 2ln_{set}$ elements) are usually non-zero. For the rest of the matrix ($n_{set} \times n_{set}$ submatrix) the element a_{i_1, i_2} may be non-zero only if the two stars i_1 and i_2 are simultaneously in the combined FOV at some instant (so that an angle measurement exists).

Thus, a necessary (but not sufficient) condition for $a_{i_1 i_2} \neq 0$ is that

$$\gamma - \Phi < |w_{i_1} - w_{i_2}| < \gamma + \Phi \tag{3}$$

or

$$|w_{i_1} - w_{i_2}| < \Phi \tag{4}$$

($w_{i_1} - w_{i_2}$ is taken modulo 2π for minimum length). Given w_{i_1} , there are three intervals of w_{i_2} for which $a_{i_1 i_2}$ may be $\neq 0$, viz.

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 &w_{i_2} \in [w_{i_1} - \gamma - \Phi, w_{i_1} - \gamma + \Phi] \\
 &w_{i_2} \in [w_{i_1} + \gamma - \Phi, w_{i_1} + \gamma + \Phi] \\
 &w_{i_2} \in [w_{i_1} - \Phi, w_{i_1} + \Phi]
 \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{5}$$

The combined length of the three intervals is 6Φ , or a fraction $3\Phi/\pi$ of the circle. It is concluded that the filling factor (fraction of non-zero elements) of the $n_{set} \times n_{set}$ submatrix (excluding the diagonal) is less than $3\Phi/\pi$. The diagonal is of course always non-zero. The filling factor of the complete matrix is therefore less than

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{max} &= (l + n_{set})^{-2} \left[l^2 + 2ln_{set} + n_{set} + \frac{3\Phi}{\pi} (n_{set}^2 - n_{set}) \right] \\
 &\approx \frac{2l}{n_{set}} + \frac{3\Phi}{\pi} \tag{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

EX. $l = 25, n_{set} = 1785, \Phi = 0.9^\circ$ gives $f_{max} = 0.043$;
 $l = 50$ increases f_{max} to 7.1%. The actual filling may be perhaps $\sim 75\%$ of f_{max} . (?)

3. On the structure of Step-1 matrix

If the stars are numbered after increasing ω_i , the non-zero elements of the n_{set}^2 submatrix will have a particular structure outlined below.

The ~~number~~ number density of stars per unit abscissa angle, $\frac{di}{d\omega_i} = \rho(\omega)$, is the areal star density

$R = n_s / 4\pi$ times the ^{angular} width of the band on the sky covered by the set. Thus, approximately,

$$\rho(\omega) = \frac{n_s}{4\pi} \cdot \left(\Phi + \frac{1}{2}(m_0-1)\Phi|\sin \omega| \right), \tag{6}$$

if ω is counted from one of the nodes. Max and min values are

$$\begin{cases} \rho_{min} = \rho(0) = \rho(\pi) = \frac{n_s}{4\pi} \Phi = 125 \text{ rad}^{-1} & (n_s=10^5, \Phi=0.9^\circ) \\ \rho_{max} = \rho(\frac{\pi}{2}) = \rho(\frac{3\pi}{2}) = \frac{m_0+1}{2} \rho_{min} = 375 \text{ rad}^{-1} & (m_0=5) \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

The number of stars between the p and f axes of the telescope (basic angle γ) is

$$n_\gamma(\omega) = \int_{\omega-\gamma/2}^{\omega+\gamma/2} \rho(\omega') d\omega', \tag{8}$$

as function of the abscissa (ω) of the x axis (between p and f).

n_γ varies between

$$\begin{cases} n_{\gamma min} = n_\gamma(0) = n_\gamma(\pi) = \rho_{min} \left[\gamma + (m_0-1)(1-\cos \frac{\gamma}{2}) \right] = 236 & (\gamma=68.5^\circ) \\ n_{\gamma max} = n_\gamma(\pm \frac{\pi}{2}) = \rho_{min} \left[\gamma + (m_0-1) \sin \frac{\gamma}{2} \right] = 431 & \end{cases} \tag{9}$$

The field-width $\pm \Phi$ corresponds roughly to ± 5 stars; in addition, there is a statistical uncertainty of the numbers n_j of the order of $\sqrt{n_j} \sim 15-20$. Accounting for these margins, the n_{set}^2 submatrix will look something like this: ($m_0=5$)

(FIG. 3)

The non-zero elements are confined to the shaded ~~to~~ strips. The origin of the star numbering is chosen so that the minimum bandwidth $n_{jmin} + margin \approx 250$ is obtained in the first row. Then it can be seen that the complete matrix (including the l "global" unknowns) has the bordered-banded structure in Fig. 4. We have ($m_0=5$):

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 n' &= \text{number of unknowns} \approx 1810 \\
 l' &= \text{border width} = l + 250 \approx 275 \\
 m' &= \text{bandwidth} \approx n_{jmax} \approx 450
 \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Note that proper choice of origin for the star numbering is essential for reducing the bandwidth.

Using the estimate by de Vegt & Ebrer (MNRAS, 167, 169) for the computing time

$$t = C \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} n' m'^2 + n' m' l' + 2 n' m' + n' l' \right),$$

where

$$C \approx 0.2 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ h for CDC 7600, and}$$

$$C \approx 1.2 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ h for RC8000 (?),}$$

we find:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} n' = 1810 \\ m' = 450 \\ l' = 275 \end{array} \right\} \Rightarrow t = 0.49 \text{ h (RC8000) per set}$$

Compare with full matrix ($m' = n' = 1810, l' = 0$)

$\Rightarrow t = 3.6 \text{ h per set, so that the time-saving factor is about } 0.14. \text{ This does not change significantly if } l \text{ is increased to } 50.$